

Attitude of Students Toward Biology Practical in Senior Secondary Schools and its Effect on their Performance

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Abstract

Attitude plays a central role in determining the future of individuals in the field of science. Students' attitude towards science influences their academic performance. Recognizing as well as influencing students' attitudes is important in educational research studies. Even though there has been series of research into students' attitudes to science, there is very scanty research into the attitudes of students to Biology practical. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to examine students' attitude toward Biology practical work and the extent to which such attitude influences students' achievement in Biology. Thus, this study is carried out on students' attitude toward four dimensions of Biology practical work namely, interest, career, importance and difficulty. The study used a 30-item Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) to measure students' attitudes toward Biology practical work. The data were obtained from 250 secondary school students from ten secondary schools in Ogbomosho. Mean and analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a positive and negative effect of attitude toward Biology achievement. The study also showed that the majority of students in Ogbomosho have positive attitudes towards Biology practical work although it does not motivate them to pursue a career in Biology beyond secondary school. The author concludes that the way and manner in which practical work is conducted may negatively influence their achievement in the subject. It is, therefore, recommended that educational materials should be provided for the students in the schools and motivational extra lessons should be organised for those students with low morale as regard positive attitude toward Biology practical.

Keywords: Academic performance; Behaviour; Future career: Interest

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Introduction

There is growing attention not only from scientific community but also from various fields that how an ordinary people perceive science. A large number of research studies in science education merely devoted to the understanding of how we can improve the quantity and quality of science education and improving enrolment rate in different courses and degrees related to science. One of the key factors in science learning is students' attitudes and, in fact, a positive attitude toward science can enhance students' interest in science and science careers (Shahzad, Naveed and Sadia, 2022). Attitude is an important concept to understand human behaviour. It is defined as a complex mental state involving beliefs and feelings (Syyeda, 2016). He goes further to define attitude as the tendency to react in a certain way towards a designed class of stimuli. Attitude has been defined as a mental and neutral state of readiness, organised through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related. People's attitudes towards their profession have an effect on their performance. This case is also valid for the profession of teaching (Gara and Asrat, 2014). Attitude plays an important role towards the future of science students. Students' attitude towards science affects their academic performance. According to Mazana, Suero- Montero and Olifage (2019), there are some factors that can affect attitude in the place of work or in the schools. Some examples of those factors are the inadequate funds of schools, lack of parent and community support, family background, broken home, poorly equipped laboratory and inadequate salaries.

Furthermore, attitude is a complex and unique concept, defined as the predisposition to think, spirits or preferences that an individual has about an attitudinal object, based on his or her belief about the object, which can be positive or negative. As stated by Mazana et al. (2019), "attitude refers to a learned tendency of a person to respond positively or negatively towards an object, situation, concept or another person". Attitude consists of three major aspects, which include behavioural, cognitive, and affective (Yuorsuu, 2024). Any concept that specifies an individual's feeling of likeness or dislike to anything is termed his/her attitude towards that item. In addition to that, Crano and Priskin (2006) moved further that attitude can be considered as consisting of components such as cognitive (information, opinions and thoughts), affective (feeling, liking and disliking) and behavioural (tendency to action).

The attitude that one has towards a particular object makes it possible to decide whether the considered object is good or bad, pleasant or unpleasant, advantageous or disadvantageous, important or irrelevant (Crano and Priskin, 2006; Oluwatelure and Oloruntegbe, 2010). Attitude can be a method, disposition, feeling or condition in respect of an individual or object, particularly of the mind. It is important for Biology teachers to ensure that students have positive attitudes in Biology subject. Studies have shown that the way students are taught in Biology classrooms is not interesting to them (Khan and Ali, 2012). Student's success in Biology is affected by their attitudes. To enhance their achievement, it is good to identify what type of attitudes they have shown as to help them in a certain discipline (Khan and Ali, 2012). Attitudes are like academic achievement because they are significant factors in ensuring students success.

Biology

Biology as a discipline tends to study all living things and their interactions in the biosphere. Biology is also the study of plants and animals including human beings like ourselves. As a science subject, Biology helps students to develop such practical skills in experimental work as observation, accurate recording, logical reasoning and effective manipulation of equipment. Biology as an elective science subject is taught at upper secondary level in Nigeria. Shahzad, Naveed and Sadia (2022) opined that Biology plays an important role in industrialization and in other sectors of the economy. Biology, because of its practical nature, trains students to learn the different concepts and skills needed to solve the problems of everyday life. The study of biology enables the learner to acquire essential knowledge in order to control the environment beneficial for an individual, family or community.

Literature revealed that there are many approaches to conducting practical biology lessons but yet achievement is still low among students (Hinneh, 2017). However, there was no vivid demonstration of the influence of students' attitudes and their achievement in science as most of the literatures were based on teachers' data. Another area of concern is in regard to research approach and data collection method. This study integrates and coordinates the extent to which practical work relates to students' attitudes as well as their achievement in Biology. This is not clearly provided in the most empirical literatures reviewed as recorded by Hinneh (2017). Also, little is known about students' attitudes towards Biology in Oyo State. It is hoped that this study will identify how students perceived Biology to be and it will help to improve their interest in Biology, and in consequence, their academic achievement in Biology.

As present, education is dynamic and multiplicity in policies, methods and procedure can be clearly observed. At different levels of education system, change is always welcomed as per required but change should always be in harmony with certain aspects i.e. society, religion, state, etc. The present situation calls for comprehensive change in almost every level of education so that practical and dynamic approach can be given to existing and new field of education. The crux of this modern education is to awaken the hidden curiosity and interest of the learner, nourishing his behaviours, attitudes and believes in order to develop basic and essential skills of lifelong learning and ability to think critically and to judge himself and others in a more beneficial manner (Samreen, Sufiana and Malik, 2012; Shahzad et al., 2022)

Methodology

Population of the Study

The population of focus is made up of all senior secondary schools in Ogbomoso and environ at the time of this study. The targeted population of interest involve selected Senior Secondary School students that are in (SSS 3) because they are preparing for their final examinations. This group of students may have their attitude affecting their academic performance in biology and other subjects either negatively or positively. Also, these groups of students are on the verge of transcending into tertiary institutions to pursue higher degrees. Consequently, their feelings, beliefs, perceptions, and experiences about the subject may impact their choice of

programs and career prospects. Therefore, it is important to investigate the causes of poor performance in the subject so that probable interventions can be suggested for remediation.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study employed survey design. According to Dillman, Smyth and Christian (2014), the survey design is a design that offers the quantitative description of emanating patterns, views and attitudes of a population and tests for the relationships existing between the variables of interest by focusing on just a fraction of the population. Employing this design provided an insightful as well as a vigorous methodological approach to exploring the levels of associations between students' attitudes and their academic. This approach is specifically compatible with the research topic as it proficiently gathers a wide range of data, explores attitudes in-depth, facilitates quantitative analysis, enables comparative assessments, provides longitudinal insights and directly correlates attitudes with academic performance (Dillman *et al.*, 2014; Field, 2013). However, simple random sampling was used to select participants from the targeted population (year three students). This offers every student within the targeted population equal chances of being selected for the study. The total population used was two hundred and fifty students collected from ten secondary schools. The present study was carried out both in public and private secondary schools in Ogbomoso.

Research Instruments

The instrument was a 30 - item structured questionnaire which was in four (4) sections (A, B, C and D). The questions were used to test the main four hypotheses of this research work. Section A was designed to collect information on Interest toward Biology practical; section B collected information on future career in biology section, C collected information on the benefits of Biology practical work while section D collected information on difficulty of biology practical work in the laboratory. The respondents were asked to respond to the questions on a five- point Likert Scale of strongly agree (SA), agree (A), undecided (U), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). The statistical method used for testing four hypotheses mentioned in this research work was analysis of variance (ANOVA) while the simple descriptive statistics of mean to answer attitude of the students whereby a mean cut-off point of 3.00 was used for decision making. Any mean score of 3.00 and above was accepted as having the desired influence while any mean score below 3.00 was rejected as not having influence.

Validity and Reliability

The instruments for measuring the attitudes of students toward Biology practical were carefully constructed and validated by the researcher, colleagues and lecturers. Colleague teachers of biology and a specialist in science education programmes independently examined the instruments and suggested their inputs, which were incorporated resulting in the final instruments.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to examine students' attitude towards Biology practical work and how such attitude affects their academic achievement in Biology. The study sought to achieve the following objectives:

Objective 1: To determine the extent to which students interest differs in their attitudes toward practical work in biology.

Objective 2: To examine the extent to which future career in Biology influence the attitude of students toward Biology practical work.

Objective 3: To examine the extent to which students' attitudes toward importance of Biology influence their academic achievement in biology practical work.

Objective 4: To determine the extent of difficulty encountered by the students during biology practical work influence their attitudes towards academic performance in Biology practical work.

To attain these objectives, four null hypotheses were posited and tested:

Null hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between interest of students and students' attitudes toward Biology practical.

Null hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between future career in biology and attitudes of the students toward Biology practical.

Null hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between importance of biology and attitudes of students toward Biology practical work.

Null hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between difficulty encountered in Biology practical work and attitudes of students toward Biology practical.

Results

Table 1: Interest and attitude of the students toward biology practical work

Items	Attitude of the students					Mean (π)	Remarks
	Strongly agreed (SA) (5)	Agreed (A) (4)	Undecided (U) (3)	Disagreed (D) (2)	Strongly disagreed (SD) (1)		
1. Practical work in my biology lesson is exciting	70 28%	70 28%	40 16%	50 20%	20 8%	3.48	Agreed
2. I like to be involved in practical work	60 24%	65 26%	30 12%	40 16%	55 22%	3.14	Agreed
3. Doing practical work is my favourite part of Biology study	30 12%	40 16%	45 18%	80 32%	55 22%	2.64	Disagreed
4. I always anticipate doing practical work	70 28%	80 32%	40 16%	30 12%	30 12%	3.52	Agreed
5. I enjoy doing practical work in Biology lesson	60 24%	70 28%	20 8%	50 20%	50 20%	3.16	Agreed
6. The way Biology practical work is done, makes learning Biology easier	70 28%	60 24%	30 12%	50 20%	40 16%	3.28	Agreed
Total	360	385	205	300	250	3.20	Agreed

The result of data analysis presented in Table 1 showed that each of the items on Table 1 has a mean range 2.64 - 3.52 while the cluster mean value for the groups were 3.20, which implies that respondents agreed that interest influence students' academic performance in biology work.

Table 2: Future career in Biology and attitude of the students toward biology practical work

Items	Attitude of the students						Mean (π)	Remarks
	Strongly agreed (SA) (5)	Agreed (A) (4)	Undecided (U) (3)	Disagreed (D) (2)	Strongly disagreed (SD) (1)			
1. I like watching natural history films; I would like therefore make a career in this field	80 32%	70 28%	40 16%	30 12%	30 12%	3.56	Agreed	
2. Biology knowledge is necessary for my future career	70 28%	85 34%	25 10%	50 20%	20 8%	3.54	Agreed	
3. It is easy to do well in practical work than in theory	60 24%	70 28%	30 12%	50 20%	50 16%	3.28	Agreed	
4. My biology teacher is my personal model; I would like to work like him	70 28%	60 24%	25 10%	55 22%	40 16%	3.30	Agreed	
5. My future career is independent from biology knowledge	40 16%	50 20%	30 12%	70 28%	60 24%	2.76	Disagreed	
6. I would like to be a biologist	70 28%	70 28%	40 16%	50 20%	20 8%	3.48	Agreed	
Total	390	405	190	305	230	3.32	Agreed	

The result of data analysis presented in Table 2 showed that each of the items on Table has a mean range 2.76 - 3.56 while the cluster mean value for the groups were 3.32, which implies that respondents agreed that future career in biology, be it science or arts influence students' academic performance in biology.

Table 3: The importance or benefits of biology and attitude of the students toward Biology practical work

Items	Attitude of the students					Mean (π)	Remarks
	Importance or benefits of biology	Strongly agreed (SA) (5)	Agreed (A) (4)	Undecided (U) (3)	Disagreed (D) (2)		
1. Biology helps in the development of my conceptual skills	75 30%	65 26%	30 12%	40 16%	40 16%	3.38	Agreed
2. Biology is important in comparison with other courses	80 32%	90 36%	10 4%	30 12%	40 16%	3.56	Agreed
3. Biology knowledge is essential for understanding other courses and phenomenon	65 26%	70 28%	20 8%	50 20%	45 18%	3.24	Agreed
4. Nobody needs biology knowledge	10 4%	20 8%	10 4%	80 32%	130 72%	1.80	Disagreed
5. The knowledge of biology improves the quality of lives	110 44%	90 36%	05 2%	30 12%	15 6%	4.00	Agreed
6. Practical work makes complicated concepts easier	80 32%	70 28%	36 14.4%	34 13.6%	30 12%	3.54	Agreed
7. I learn how to draw biological diagrams better in Biology practical work	75 30%	70 28%	35 14%	30 12%	40 16%	3.44	Agreed
8. Practical Biology work helps me to see how things work in nature	80 32%	60 24%	30 12%	45 18%	35 14%	3.42	Agreed
9. Practical work helps me develop the spirit of team work	70 28%	85 34%	20 8%	40 16%	35 14%	3.48	Agreed
10. Practical work increases my concentration than if I am just sitting down listening to teacher	65 26%	85 34%	20 8%	40 16%	40 16%	3.38	Agreed
11. Doing practical work helps improve my knowledge	70 28%	75 30%	25 10%	50 20%	30 12%	3.42	Agreed
12. Practical work prepares me adequately for examination	80 32%	70 28%	22 8.8%	48 19.2%	30 12%	3.49	Agreed
Total	860	850	263	487	510	3.35	Agreed

The result of data analysis presented in Table 3 showed that each of the items on the table has a mean range 1.80 – 4.00 while the cluster mean value for the groups were 3.35, which implies that respondents agreed that importance or benefits of Biology influence students’ academic performance in biology work. They also agreed that everybody need the knowledge of Biology for improving their quality lives.

Table 4: The difficulty and problem encountered by the students during practical work and their attitude toward academic performance in biology practical work

Items	Attitude of the students						Mean (π)	Remarks
	Strongly agreed (SA) (5)	Agreed (A) (4)	Undecided (U) (3)	Disagreed (D) (2)	Strongly Disagreed (SD) (1)			
1. I often have difficulties to understand basic concepts of biology practical.	79 31.6%	70 28%	30 12%	50 20%	21 8.4%	3.50	Agreed	
2. Biology diagram rules are very difficult to obey	110 44%	70 28%	10 4%	40 16%	20 8%	3.84	Agreed	
3. I found it very easy to handle Biology Equipment effectively	30 12%	40 16%	50 20%	60 24%	70 28%	2.60	Disagreed	
4. Our Biology teacher asks us to draw some specimens in every practical class	50 20%	70 28%	40 16%	40 16%	50 20%	3.10	Agreed	
5. I never use any Biology equipment in practical class.	50 20%	50 20%	50 20%	50 20%	50 20%	3.00	Agreed	
6. Drawing some specimens during practical class is cumbersome.	40 16%	30 12%	55 22%	65 26%	60 24%	2.66	Disagreed	
Total	359	330	235	305	246	3.12	Agreed	

The result of data analysis presented in Table 4 showed that each of the items on the Table has a mean range 2.60– 3.84 while the cluster mean value for the groups were 3.12, which implies that respondents agreed that the difficult encounter during Biology practical work influence students’ academic performance in biology work.

Null hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between interest of students and students’ attitudes toward Biology practical.

Table 5 indicates that the calculated ANOVA of 0.592 is lesser than the critical value of 0.626 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the interest of the students and attitudes of Biology students toward Biology practical

Null hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between future career in Biology and attitudes of the students toward Biology practical.

Table 5 indicates that the calculated ANOVA of 1.274 is greater than the critical value of 0.304 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between the future career of Biology students and attitudes of students’ toward academic performance in Biology practical.

Table 5: The summary of students’ attitude toward Biology practical and how it affects their academic performance in biology

		ANOVA					
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Interest of the students	Between Groups	831.467	3	277.156	0.592		0.626
	Within Groups	12177.500	26	468.365			
	Total	13008.967	29				
Future career of Biology	Between Groups	1036.667	3	345.556	1.274		0.304
	Within Groups	7050.000	26	271.154			
	Total	8086.667	29				
Importance of Biology	Between Groups	1407.450	3	469.150	3.853		0.021
	Within Groups	3165.917	26	121.766			
	Total	4573.367	29				
Difficulty of practical work	Between Groups	404.783	3	134.928	0.723		0.547
	Within Groups	4852.583	26	186.638			
	Total	5257.367	29				

Null hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between importance of Biology and attitudes of students toward Biology practical.

Table 5 indicates that the calculated ANOVA of 3.853 is greater than the critical value of 0.021 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between importance of Biology and attitudes of the students toward academic performance in Biology practical.

Null hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between difficulty encounter in biology practical work and attitudes of students toward Biology practical.

Table 5 indicates that the calculated ANOVA of 0.723 is greater than the critical value of 0.547 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between difficulty of practical work and attitudes of students toward academic performance in Biology practical.

Discussion

The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between students’ attitude towards biology practical work and their academic performance in Biology at the secondary level in Ogbomoso, Oyo State. This was confirmed by the qualitative result, which found that though students recognize the importance of practical work, very few expressed interest in pursuing career in Biology related fields. This concurs with those of Kalender and Berberoglu (2009), Hofstein and Mamlok-Naaman (2011), Musasia, Abacha and MembaEmmahBiyoyo (2012) and Sharpe (2012) that students’ attitudes toward practical work is positive but the experience cannot influence their achievement in Biology. However, the finding is contrary to those of Hussaini, Foong and Kamar (2015) and Odom, Stoddard and LaNasa (2007) who found that using practical hands-on

activities can improve student's achievement in science and the daily use of practical activities yield the greatest positive impact on students' achievement in science. One explanation for this may be due to the fact that the manner in which these practical works were carried on in this study did not involve pure hands-on activities.

Furthermore, this study revealed that students' attitude to the future career, importance of Biology and difficulty of practical work significantly influence their achievement in Biology while their attitudes concerning interest do not significantly influence their achievement in Biology. It can be concluded that even though students demonstrate some level of positive attitude towards practical work in Biology in terms of its future career, importance and difficulty of practical work, the experience students gain from doing practical work as regard biology lessons do not motivate them to create interest in pursue career in biology beyond secondary school. A possible explanation could be the manner in which practical work is carried out in secondary schools negatively influences their achievement in the subject or it may be the hatred some students have to the odour of preservative chemicals in laboratory. Also, this could be as a result of lacking basic Biology concepts at beginning. In other words, students' general attitude towards practical work is positive but cannot motivate their achievement in biology.

Educational implications of the study can be summarized as follows; frequent use of specimens in Biology lessons and/or practical works may increase students' interest toward biology. Interest in biology should be developed for students in particular. Because students showed low interest in biology, their interest should be increased perhaps through contact with professional biologists and their ideas about professional biologists and the role of biology knowledge in daily life should be investigated deeply. Biology subjects should be re-evaluated in terms of low interest in this topic frequently reported by respondents. Finally, more research should be carried out on the subjects like, attitude of biology teachers and their impact on students' interest, and attitude of biology teachers toward academic performance of biology students. Findings of such studies may significantly contribute to improve Biology education in the future.

Conclusion

In conclusions, practical work is considered an essential part of science education in secondary schools, but this study has demonstrated that its relevance is under a serious threat. The study found that students display similar attitude towards practical work. They consider practical work as important part of learning Biology and activity during Biology practical lesson as a route part in making learning of Biology easier. In addition to that, the study found that students' attitude about the importance of practical work significantly influences their achievement in Biology while their attitude concerning interest in practical work does not significantly influence their achievement in Biology. It can be concluded that even though students demonstrate some level of positive attitude towards practical work in Biology in terms of its importance, the knowledge students' gain from doing practical work in the biology lessons does not motivate them to want to pursue a career in Biology beyond secondary school. A possible explanation could be the manner in which practical work is carried out in secondary school negatively influences their achievement

in the subject. In other words, students' general attitude towards practical work is positive but cannot influence their achievement in Biology.

Educational implications and recommendations:

The following educational implications and recommendations are made:

1. School Administrators should take the lead to emphasize the essential role of practical work in learning biology. This will require schools to procure and provide laboratory resources to enhance teaching and learning in biology lessons.
2. Teachers should provide students the opportunity to engage in frequent practical works relevant to the condition and topics. This will make students to develop positive attitude towards practical work and enhance their achievement in biology and in science general even beyond secondary school.
3. It is recommended that biology teachers should use teaching methodologies that ensured students' positive attitude towards biology at the secondary level.
4. The majority of the students also indicate in the questionnaire that the practical work in biology is interesting and makes them to like biology; therefore, teachers should provide enough specimens to generate positive attitudes in biology.
5. Students who wish to pursue career in science should develop positive realistic attitude in order to improve their long-term achievement. In this case, students need to take their practical lessons serious and carry out extra practical work in biology.

References

- Crano, W. D, and Priskin, R. (2006). *Attitudes and Persuasions*. Ann.Revis.Psychol. 57:345-374.
- Dillman, D. A., Smyth, J. D. and Christian, L. M. (2014). *Internet, phone, mail, and mixed-mode surveys: The tailored design method*. (4th ed). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics: And sex and drugs and Rock "N" Roll*, 4th Edition, SAGE, Los Angeles, London, New Delh.
- Gara, L. and Asrat, D. (2014). Attitude of teachers towards the use of active learning methods. net/publication/237759651: 1-5 <https://www.researchgate>.
- Hinne J. T. (2017), Attitude towards practical work and students' achievement in biology: A case of a private senior secondary school in Gaborone, Botswana. *Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM)*, 13(4): 6-11 www.iosrjournals.org DOI: 10.9790/5728-1304010611
- Hofstein, A., and Mamlok-Naaman, R. (2011). High-school students' attitudes toward and interest in learning chemistry. *Educación Química*, 22(2): 90-102.
- Hussaini, I, Foong, L. M. and Kamar, Y. (2015). Attitudes of secondary school students towards biology as a school subject in Birninkebbi metropolis, *Nigeria. Int J Res Rev*. 2(10): 596-600.
- Kalender, I. and Berberoglu, G. (2009). An Assessment of factors related to science achievement of Turkish students. *International Journal of Science Education*, 31(10): 1379-1394.
- Khan, G. N., and Ali, A. (2012). Higher secondary school students' attitude towards chemistry. *Asian Social Science Journal*, 8(6): 165.

- Mazana, Y. M., Suero Montero, C., and Olifage, C. R. (2019). Investigating students' attitude towards learning mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(1): 207-231. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/3997>.
- Musasia, A. M., Abacha, O. A., and MembaEmmahBiyoyo, M. E. (2012). Effect of practical work in physics on girls' performance, attitude change and skills acquisition in the form two-form three secondary schools' transition in Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 2(23): 221-230.
- Odom, A., Stoddard, E. R., and LaNasa, S. M. (2007). Teachers' practices and middle school science achievements. *International Journal of Science Education*, 29(11), 1329-1346.
- Oluwatelure, T. A., and Oloruntegbe, K. O. (2010). Effects of parental involvement on students attitude and performance in science. *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 4(1), 001-009.
- Samreen A., Sufiana, and Malik, K. (2012). Use of audio visual aids for effective teaching of biology at secondary schools level. *Elixir International Journal, Elixir Leadership Mgmt.* 50, 10597-10605, www.elixirpublishers.com
- Shahzad A., Naveed S, and Sadia J, (2022). Students' Attitude towards Biology and Academic Achievement in Biology at Secondary Level, in Islamabad, Pakistan. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 10(5): 268-275. DOI: 10.12691/ education -10-5-1.
- Sharpe, R. M. (2012). Secondary school students' attitudes to practical work in school science (Doctoral Dissertation). Retrieved from <http://eprints.lincoln.ac.uk/14657/1>
- Syyeda, F. (2016). Understanding attitudes towards mathematics (ATM) using a multimodal modal model: An exploratory case study with secondary school children in England. *Cambridge Open-Review Educational Research Journal*, 3, 32-62.
- Yuorsuu, S. N. M. (2024). Home economics students' attitudes towards biology and how it impacts their academic performance. *European Journal of Health and Biology Education*, 11(1), 21-27.